

Using broad beans to diversify living mulch cover during the winter season

Problem

Cover cropping can be challenging in biointensive market gardening systems due to long cropping periods, while the resulting crop residues may hinder rapid bed preparation between crops.

Solution

Legumes can protect winter soil-bed coverage as living plants, and certain broad beans (*Vicia faba* L. var. *major*), can overwinter well. This allows farmers to diversify their overwintering crops, improve crop rotations, and expand their range of fresh produce.

Benefits

Overwintering crops can deliver benefits which are similar to those of cover crops, including: soil surface protection; reduced soil erosion; presence of a living root system that supports soil biota. These effects enhance key soil ecosystem services, such as nutrient cycling and water infiltration; and so, contribute to improved soil health. Depending on the farmer's management decisions, the crop can be terminated in spring and used as a green manure; or maintained and harvested as grain (still leaving nutritionally crop residues for the soil). Horticultural faba bean varieties are a relatively underutilised as fresh (green grain) produce - despite offering multiple health benefits and diverse culinary uses and therefore represent a potential niche crop with economic value.

Applicability box

Theme

Novel cover crops for overwintering living soil cover

Keywords

Cover crop, faba bean, broad bean, overwintering, living mulch

Context

Europe (and international)

Application time

Autumn sowing, overwintering period

Required time

One day for sowing in Autumn, min. 5 months (Oct/Nov- till Feb-March)

Period of impact

Winter growing period, soil improvement for next crop

Equipment

No specific tool

Best in

Biointensive fixed bed system, market gardening, organic horticulture

Practical recommendations

- **Sowing (Figure 1):** Sowing time is critical, as crops sown too early may suffer frost damage, while late sowing can increase vulnerability to adverse conditions. Although the traditional sowing period for faba beans is February–March, milder winters associated with climate change allow for successful sowing from the second half of October to mid-November.
- **Winter protection (Figure 1):** If winter temperatures fall below -5°C , the use of a protective fleece is recommended to prevent frost damage.
- **Harvesting and plant protection (Fig. 2):** When crops are maintained for harvest, preventive plant protection measures against fungal diseases are advised, as late-spring heat stress can increase susceptibility to infections.
- **Intercropping:** Faba beans (var. minor, field beans) can be intercropped with peas, cereals (e.g. rye), or other cover crops in Continental regions to enhance ecological benefits.

Figure 1. Sowing (mid Oct), sprouting (mid Nov) and winter cover with fleece of Faba bean. Photo: Alfréd Szilágyi, Agri Kulti.

Figure 2. Faba bean is a good overwintering crop for diversifying biointensive gardens. Photo: Alfréd Szilágyi, Agri Kulti

Further information

Video

- A Complete Guide from Autumn to Spring Planting: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oO3P_TJx_so (English)

Further reading

- What Is the Best Cover Crop for a Vegetable Garden? <https://themarketgardener.com/farming-techniques/what-is-the-best-cover-crop-for-a-vegetable-garden/>

Weblinks

- How to Grow Broad beans: <https://www.rhs.org.uk/vegetables/broad-beans/grow-your-own>
- How to Grow Broad beans: <https://www.gardenorganic.org.uk/expert-advice/how-to-grow/growing-guides/vegetables-herbs-guides/how-to-grow-broad-bean>
- Faba Bean Cover Crop Factsheet: <https://www.nrcs.usda.gov/sites/default/files/2025-07/Faba%20Bean%20Cover%20Crop%20Fact%20Sheet.pdf>

About this practice abstract

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Permalink: <https://zenodo.org/records/19473283>
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LegumES – Valorization of ecosystem services provided by legume crops - aims to share, showcase, co-develop, and implement the knowledge, key agronomic practices, methodologies, and tools which will allow optimized legume-based systems, and valorization of the ES benefits provided.

Project website: www.legumesproject.eu

Funding

Funded by
the European Union

UK Research
and Innovation

Project funded by

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

LegumES has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101135512. Its work is supported by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) through the Horizon Europe Guarantee scheme Grant Agreement and by the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) under grant No. 23.00034 and 23.00645.

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union, UK Research and Innovation ((UKRI), European Research Executive Agency (REA) or the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI). Neither the European Union nor any other granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Funded by
the European Union

UK Research
and Innovation

Project funded by

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI